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**Accessibility of Bilingual Cross-Border e-Commerce in GBA: A Case Study of
Traditional Chinese Crafts**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is two-fold. First, it attempts to analyse channels for the dissemination of traditional Chinese crafts in GBA in order to establish a strong foundation for the promotion of crafts as well as the economic development of the region. Second, it explores the accessibility of bilingual cross-border e-commerce for advertising crafts in GBA. The results of the study suggest that bilingual cross-border e-commerce is highly feasible for the marketing of crafts. In the backdrop of innovation and entrepreneurship education, it is imperative to take advantage of the opportunity to develop cross-border e-commerce and promote the same through foreign language skills simultaneously.

INTRODUCTION

In light of the steady growth of international economy and improvement in people's living standards, the commercialisation of traditional Chinese crafts is bound to progress significantly. As far back as the Ming and Qing Dynasty, people began to engage in the manufacture of crafts such as wood carvings. After the founding of the People's Republic of China, the production of such crafts progressed further and gained widespread appreciation. It seems that the development of the craft industry in each province helped to cultivate a wide range of talents. However, the Internet was yet to be invented back then to promote the crafts industry. Therefore, the advertising of crafts on the Internet has significant research value in the current scenario. This paper will focus on promoting the craft industry overseas and expanding its marketing so that crafts from the Guangdong-Hong Kong-Macao Greater Bay Area (henceforth GBA) can simultaneously be expanded. Given the scope of development in GBA, bilingual services are more conducive to stimulating cross-border e-commerce of crafts as well as regional economic growth. This paper aims to investigate the accessibility of bilingual cross-border e-commerce in GBA for marketing traditional Chinese crafts, which has high research and application value. The aim of this paper is to explore the promotion of bilingual cross-border e-commerce to market Chinese traditional crafts in GBA. Bilingual services have become an indispensable means to promote domestic products in overseas markets. When the domestic consumer market is saturated, it is important to open up new markets. With the rapid development of productivity and the improvement of people's standard of living, the Internet has become an indispensable tool. A dedicated network platform is currently an important aspect of many industries. The use of cross-border websites can prevent single sales channels, and while using the Internet to open up a larger market, cross-border websites with bilingual services will be integrated with the dissemination of crafts, giving novel developments in the inheritance and the advertising of crafts. Moreover, crafts, as a symbol of Chinese traditional culture, represent their hard work and strong spirit. Extending bilingual cross-border e-commerce service to

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sell crafts will also enhance the influence of Chinese culture at home and abroad, thus boosting Chinese people's self-confidence.

Literature Review

Considering either cross-border e-commerce or marketing of crafts in GBA, there are few publications directly related to the current research. Liu (2019) contends that there are certain advantages of cross-border e-commerce in GBA. Specifically, cross-border businesses are highly complementary. The Free Trade Zone in GBA has certain advantages as well as challenges. For example, there is a shortage of talent in the cross-border e-commerce industry. There are only a few large cross-border e-commerce platforms. The logistics warehousing system needs to be improved. The efficiency of cross-border fund payment is also not well-established. Liu further offers suggestions to alleviate the problem. There is a need to initiate efforts to promote cross-border talents, especially through educational institutions and cooperations. It is imperative to develop a three-dimensional (government, cooperation and customer) logistics warehousing system for cross-border e-commerce. Furthermore, it is highly beneficial to reduce payment costs through offshore companies, to improve capital turnover efficiency and to fulfill the integration of government services.

Peng (2019) offers solutions to address existing problems in cross-border logistics in GBA from two aspects. First, the development system of cross-border logistics is not well established. Second, the progress of the cross-border logistics industry is uneven. The entire logistics system does not include information sharing mechanisms and support from big data platforms. Cooperation among logistics enterprises is neither successful nor sustainable. Additionally, there is a lack of local talent in cross-border e-commerce. To address these issues, he proposed the balanced development of the cross-border e-commerce logistics industry. By applying and integrating big data, information regarding cross-border e-commerce logistics can be shared so as to create a well-established logistics system. Raising the cooperation level of logistics enterprises is imperative and it gives rise to the integration of logistics enterprises. It is recommended to accelerate the construction of talents in cross-border e-commerce logistics by improving educational policies.

Bai (2016) analyses the current situation of export of crafts in China, and further recommends feasible methods and suggestions to facilitate the export of crafts effectively. The export market for Chinese crafts is extremely concentrated. Moreover, many craft companies are not strong enough to adapt to a highly competitive and integrated economy in the present scenario. The craft products are not sound in quality and are not high value-added. To address these issues, he proposed to optimise product quality based on the market overseas, to consolidate traditional markets effectively and to actively develop emerging markets such as Europe, South Africa and Latin America. In order to organise the crafts market, it is necessary to curtail unfair competition so as to expand the export of crafts. Simultaneously, in order to market crafts aggressively in international markets, craft companies should exit vicious competition, implement a unified strategy in exports and sell crafts at an ideal price.

Some consider a specific educational institution in GBA as an example to investigate the correlation between the promotion of traditional crafts and embodied practices in school education. Educational practices are introduced in the Zhuhai City Vocational College for the inheritance of traditional crafts of Cantonese jewellery carving through school-enterprise cooperation and industry-academia cooperation (Zhou and Xie, 2018).

Methodology

In this paper, one of the methods used was literature review exploring the channels for the dissemination of traditional Chinese crafts and accessibility of bilingual cross-border e-commerce in GBA. To fully understand the problems encountered in the present development of crafts and in the future, field work in two cities was carried out as the research method. The two locations – Zengcheng

and Yunfu – are rich in making crafts and exporting them to other cities in GBA. It is also widely accepted that advanced technology is the key driver of the economic growth of a region. Accordingly, this drives us to the question as to whether cross-border e-commerce employed as a new platform can stimulate the innovation of craft marketing, improvement of craftsmanship and expansion of the craft markets.

The Current Situation of Dissemination of Crafts in GBA

This paper investigates the development of crafts produced in Zengcheng and Yunfu, Guangdong, which are rich in craft production. Through field work and consultations with local experts in the crafts field, the development of craft production in these two locations are examined.

The craft of Zengcheng (olive carving) has a history dating back to hundreds of years, and the inheritance of the craft has witnessed several ups and downs. In principle, there are two ways to make crafts; one is manual production and the other is mechanical manufacturing. Manual and mechanical production have their own advantages and disadvantages. Manual production is time-consuming, and the price is much higher than that of mechanical manufacturing. The shape, size and style of handmade products are different, and each has its own characteristics. Because of its high collectibility and value appreciation, most people buy handmade crafts. Mechanical productions are more time-consuming, and are much cheaper. The shape, size and style of machine-made products are almost similar to handmad ones, but they are not well-received. Therefore, the supply of machine-made crafts is generally greater than the demand; hence, it is essential to increase the sale of machine-made crafts through cross-border e-commerce.

In the absence of dissemination channels, a narrow sales market and the influence of other artworks, the distribution of crafts has not been as successful as one might expect. Arts and crafts, once considered exceptional in the middle and the latter half of the 20th century, are almost declining. With rapid urbanisation and increasing outflow of the labour force, the inheritance of traditional crafts and the markets for these craft have been facing great challenges. Although crafts are widespread in the local area, the people living there neither pay much attention to it nor realise its value. The ornamental function of crafts is lower than its practical purpose. In brief, the growth of crafts is reducing significantly. At present, there are at least three issues hindering the development of Zengcheng crafts.

- (1) The degree of innovation for crafts is not high;
- (2) The technique of producing crafts remains traditonal;
- (3) There is a lack of systematisation in the marketing of crafts.

The crafts industry is also popular for its long history in Yunfu, Guangdong, which dates back to more than 400 years since the Ming Dynasty. Since the reforms during the last 20 yearsr, the craft industry in Yunfu has been developing rapidly, which, in turn, has resulted in the meteoric rise of the local economy. Owing to its proximity to the Pearl River Delta, Hong Kong and Macao, the Yunfu craft industry has witnessed significant success. However, in recent years, various problems have gradually emerged:

- (1) Stones for making crafts have been drying up while purchase cost is steadily increasing;
- (2) The processing technology of producing crafts cannot meet the market demand for large-scale and modern society;
- (3) The marketing mode is single and sluggish.

Meanwhile, according to the field work, the bilingual service and cross-border e-commerce sales of crafts in Zengcheng and Yunfu are not given due importance. Undoubtedly, the favorable geographical location of GBA greatly enhance the feasibility of marketing and the development of crafts. Zengcheng crafts is a class of cultural and creative products. As the field work reveals, bilingual service can be used to promote its distribution, so as to improve the cultural popularity and public acceptance of olive wood carving craft. Moreover, cross-border e-commerce enhances its sales channels, thus increasing its demand for raw materials, which in turn promotes the legacy and development of crafts.

Yunfu crafts require more bilingual services and the publicity of mainstream media for its promotion in international markets. With the new sales mode of cross-border e-commerce, it will break the passive and traditional service (waiting for customers), which is more conducive to the development of domestic and foreign sales markets.

Yet, the techniques for cross-border e-commerce logistics are inadequate and do not adapt to the development of cross-border e-commerce in GBA. Students have little practice in schools and it is difficult for them to start working in cross-border e-commerce companies immediately after their graduation. In the professional discipline of universities, teaching of e-commerce business knowledge is relatively superficial, and eventually most students do not have adequate professional knowledge regarding the field or even the terminology concerning crafts in foreign languages.

In terms of logistics, cross-border e-commerce is characterised by small orders, large batches and short acquisition cycles (Zuo, 2016). It emphasises the speed of logistics, and its primary transportation mode is via the world's express delivery system. China Post's world parcel and world express delivery systems such as DHL, FedEx and TNT are the main logistics industries. Both Xiao (2020) and Yu (2017) point out, while choosing cross-border logistics, one needs to take into consideration the overall cost and safety planning as well as the probability of customers retrieving goods. If one simply considers the cost, it will give rise to slow logistics, extend the supply time, decrease customer satisfaction, and could also result in the loss of long-term loyal customers. If one merely seeks service quality, he will be faced with high costs, and may even lose money. Although companies intend to adopt logistics warehousing such as overseas storage and all-in-one transportation after assembly, it is not suitable for small-scale companies (See Yu, 2017; Peng, 2019 and Xiao, 2020 for further discussion). It can be concluded that when cross-border logistics fail to match the rapid development of cross-border e-commerce, there is an urgent need to reform distribution logistics.

Therefore, in view of the problems encountered in the two locations that produce crafts, this paper offers constructive suggestions on the sale of crafts in GBA in combination with cross-border e-commerce, and on enhancing the design and operation of bilingual cross-border e-commerce websites, so as to expand the domestic market, enter overseas markets, cultivate proper talents and provide effective logistics.

Marketing and Promotion of Crafts in Bilingual Cross-Border e-Commerce in GBA

Under the supervision of World Trade Organization (WTO), handicrafts or crafts are witnessing great opportunities and challenges. The craft industry highly values individuality. In the absence of specificity, it is difficult for the industry to survive. Considering the development and promotion of crafts in GBA as the foundation, this paper examines the promotion of crafts in overseas markets and problems in specific marketing channels. In addition, this paper will extend the perspective to the bilingual cross-border e-commerce environment. In the wake of the rapid development of e-commerce, there is a need for enterprises to introduce continuous improvements in order to effectively use the platform to promote the development of crafts. With novel methods, technologies and channels, marketing channels of crafts can be enhanced significantly. In subsequent sections, the construction, design and operation of bilingual cross-border e-commerce webpages in GBA will be presented. Finally, solutions and recommendations to address problems will be discussed.

Construction of Bilingual Cross-border e-Commerce Website in GBA

Before constructing the website, it is necessary to compile relevant content such as information related to crafts, and organise the required text content and relevant pictures, footages, videos and the materials required for the webpage, so as to prepare for further action.

To build a bilingual cross-border e-commerce website, we need to create a comprehensive theme to publicise the information related to crafts, introduce craft companies, highlight the dynamic propaganda forecast of the craft industry and release the list of new products. All of these can be realised through this website. Simultaneously, we can market related craft products through the website to promote marketing. The website will also require plenty of skills for website operation and management, so that webpages can be developed normally and sustainably.

The presence of a domain name is equivalent to a business card. A good website cannot do without the embellishment of the domain name, just as a person is recognised by his name. Therefore, the domain name of a bilingual cross-border e-commerce website is crucial. In the absence of relevant professional knowledge, we can consult technical experts for advice, in order to build a successful website.

Choose a stable and reliable virtual host

As a worldwide platform, cross-border e-commerce websites have a relatively large number of visitors. If the website fails to open or the waiting time is long, it could leave a terrible impression in the customer, resulting in the loss of a large number of clients. Ultimately, an enterprise website represents its image in a virtual world. Therefore, to build a bilingual cross-border e-commerce website, it would be preferable to find a provider with vast experience as well as guaranteed and reliable quality.

Website program

The construction of a website also needs to take into account the need to code the website program. We can purchase an open source system from the Internet, which is effective and easy to master, and find the website program suitable for our website. It would be best to seek the help of a professional website designing company, so that technical consultation and maintenance at a later stage will be convenient and fast, and technological capabilities can also be guaranteed.

Select a website template and plan the website well

To build a suitable website, we need to have our own industry-style template. We can hire relevant designers to create and design a style template that conforms to the bilingual cross-border website based on our requirements. After completing the site template, start to plan the website, consider the relevant functions of the website, and try to plan all the functions in order to avoid frequent modifications later.

Enhance the webpage and test it online

After the webpage function is guaranteed, we are expected to enhance the appearance of the website and highlight the unique style of our bilingual cross-border e-commerce website. First, we should determine the overall planning of the whole web system, the content range and purpose, and then introduce the collected information on the website, according to the positioning of the enterprise, and adjust the details concurrently. Note that it is the Chinese and English versions of the website to be shown to customers from abroad and for overseas marketing. After the webpage design is completed, it is important to update the content of the webpage in a timely manner, as it is not always possible to change the webpage frequently. We then need to test the performance of the website. If all the functions can be used normally, it is ready to go online. To simplify and accomplish the whole process, we can use the services of professional web designers.

Focus on Innovation

In the Internet era, there is stiff competition to gain market share from opponents in the same industry. So how do we stand out among the competitors? In order to receive validation from customers, we must introduce innovation in website construction, and recreate it when needed. The society is constantly progressing, and the needs of users are consistently changing. If an enterprise cannot meet the requirements of consumers and keep pace with them, it will be eliminated. Therefore, it is widely acknowledged that only by constantly strengthening services or products can enterprises remain viable.

Design of Bilingual Cross-border e-Commerce Website in GBA

Homepage is the webpage that users enter by default when they open the browser, and it includes the personal homepage, website page, activity homepage, company homepage, etc. Website homepage design refers to the design of pictures or texts. It is a web platform that provides information (including products, services, photos, etc) to visitors through the Internet, and carries out multiple website functions, so that users can communicate and exchange transactions through webpages. As cross-border e-commerce websites in GBA are yet to be developed, a more reasonable design direction

can be drawn from several well-known cross-border e-commerce websites, such as Alibaba, eBay and Amazon. When designing cross-border e-commerce websites in GBA, we should pay attention to the following points:

Capture the cultural characteristics of countries and regions

For example, if targeting western countries, we can imbibe the characteristics of Amazon and eBay webpages that include individualistic culture; if the target audience is Asian, we can learn from the characteristics of Alibaba, and focus on collectivism culture, and make the Internet version adapt to the cultural differences of different countries and regions.

Define the types of craft needed to different groups

Crafts demand can be classified by type. For example, for western countries, pictures in the form of style and colour in line with their cultural characteristics can be used to show the characteristics of crafts, and colour differentiation is used to emphasise the visual effect of crafts to attract corresponding consumers, without using too many words or symbols; for Asian countries, the webpage can integrate the information layout of crafts, distinguished by lines, gather links and navigation of similar commodities featured, and provide consumers with sufficient knowledge about the products.

Pay attention to the cultural display of crafts

Due to the low popularity of crafts in GBA, it is necessary to introduce the product culture in the webpage so that overseas customers can understand the origin, value, development and innovation of the crafts. Simultaneously, the homepage should not only highlight the characteristics of crafts, but also attract different groups of customers. The bilingual service serves as a link and bridge for crafts and the culture it represents. For instance, pictures and videos of the corresponding crafts on the homepage show the products with strong characteristics in GBA, while the text introduction and video commentary are bilingual (Chinese and English) so that people can choose their own display mode.

Operation of Bilingual Cross-border e-Commerce Website in GBA

The content of website construction should be novel

The choice of web content must be unconventional. When designing website content, we should not copy content from other websites. We should combine our actual modalities to create a website of our own style.

The website page and name should be concise

The pages of the website should be orderly, convenient for customers to visit and effective for them to manage. A good domain name can strike a chord with people. The simpler the domain name, the more easier it is for people to recall. Like Taobao (you can find good treasures on it by the Chinese interpretation of Taobao), an effective domain name can easily make buyers consider it and buy products from it.

The content of the website should be updated in time

After the website is completed, it does not mean that the task is over; in fact, the workload increases thereafter. Since the production of webpages is temporary, one must constantly work on maintaining and updating it every day. Invalid links on the webpage should be eliminated immediately. For example, a user clicks on a link on the page, and after a long wait, he will be disappointed with your webpage if it is inaccessible. If you cannot update it in a timely manner, it is better to post information on the homepage and inform visitors that you are unable to update the homepage regularly due to unavoidable circumstances. It is recommended that you post an apology, so as to reflect accountability.

Website construction should focus on user experience

Always pay attention to the volume of website traffic and user experience. If the number of website visits increases, the site will slow down considerably. Consequently, visitor bounce rate will increase. So, if you want to increase traffic to your website, you must upgrade it to improve user experience.

Attract new visitors to your website

How do you attract visitors? For this, it is suggested that you innovate the information on the website and learn from other people's successes. Promotions should be conducted at an early stage, as well as business and festival activities. Actions such as regularly training talents, responding to customer queries, updating the website and promoting it in other well-known forums or websites can help attract customers.

Turn more visitors into consumers

When a customer clicks on the website, pictures, text, discounts, styles, etc. of the website should be adjusted appropriately in order to take into consideration the wide array of customers from different countries. The culture of each nation or region is different. Appropriate picture display conforming to national styles and aesthetics is important to induce customer transactions. It is believed that e-commerce does not pertain to selling products, but selling pictures, especially cross-border e-commerce. Every e-commerce operator is required to imbibe knowledge regarding a specific country's history, culture and society, since they are basic to understanding the local people. For instance, Chinese people like Taobao's images on the main page, while Americans like those found on Amazon (Chai, 2020).

Always consider the perspective of users

All the work of website construction is carried out in the interests of users, because real compliance with consumer needs is always from users' point of view, rather than simply beautifying the website. It is not just the product or service that is attractive, but the website layout, detailed design, colour theme and website structure are all crucial factors that greatly influence user experience.

Try to increase the average profit brought by each customer

All businesses aim to maximise profits, ranging from games to stores selling noodles. In the vein of Huang (2019), maximisation of profits can be long-term or short-term. Short-term profit refers to the profit a customer brings to you every time, while long-term customers are more valuable than short-term customers, since they comprise primary traffic, and can increase dynamic sales. Thus, we must try to regularly present good news to customers, which meets not only their needs, but also the traffic of the website. Only when the number of visitors is large enough can the transaction rate increase. Note that the management of new and old customers is different, and new customers are given preferential treatment than existing ones. New customers are more likely to receive discounts, while existing customers need to join some special activity to avail discounts. Only large discounts can be given in a limited time to better increase transaction volume.

Long-term customers have always given preference to three aspects—product, service and logistics. In relation to bilingual cross-border e-commerce, customer service is an important factor. Good customer service should provide practical support for website operation. Therefore, in addition to technical bilingual application on the website, it is essential to promote bilingual customer service. Customers are likely to be concerned about the logistics of their purchase after a long period of waiting. Therefore, a successful cross-border e-commerce should address the customer's logistics issues in an opportune and timely manner. In this manner, customers will be willing to wait for their favorite items composedly. The arrival of their purchase also lays a steady foundation for making their next shopping experience pleasant.

Solutions and Recommendations

Strengthen Internet marketing and cooperate with large enterprises

With the rapid development of technology, the use of the Internet can comprehensively help in the display of crafts in GBA. In the current era of well-developed marketing, crafts can actively rely on online media. If small and medium-sized enterprises cannot develop their own e-commerce websites, they should work in conjunction with big companies. They can cooperate with large enterprises that provide bilingual services indirectly through large-scale e-commerce, and effectively achieve online transactions. Concurrently, they can exchange and cooperate with foreign countries by holding or participating in various exhibitions or festivals, which highlights the cultural connotation of crafts and creates a batch of cultural industries carrying Guangdong's legacy. It is also suggested to give full credit to the government for overall planning and coordination, promotion of the development of crafts and enhancement of brand construction.

Establish an evaluation system of logistics service and research overseas e-commerce websites

In order to make a more accurate evaluation of the logistics service quality in cross-border e-commerce enterprises, it is necessary to establish an objective evaluation system. Since there are many uncertain indicators in the process of evaluation, we should examine the service level of cross-border logistics from an overall perspective. Whether the evaluation index is perfect and whether the weight of the evaluation index is reasonable will have a great impact on the assessment of the logistics service (Li & Shen, 2017).

We should also research overseas shopping websites. Since shopping websites of cross-border e-commerce are all over the world and the legal norms, business environment, customs and shopping preferences of countries or regions are also different, it is objectively proposed that cross-border e-commerce operators should conduct a comprehensive study of shopping websites before choosing to enter such markets, in order to avoid risks.

Cultivate international logistics talents in cross-border e-commerce environment

It is believed that in any professional business environment, the determining factor is to cultivate competencies. Talents are the first productivity of any enterprise. A cross-border e-commerce company should upgrade its current personnel training system by building a school-enterprise e-commerce talent training system. Using high-quality teaching resources of colleges and universities, and combining best practices of enterprises, we can jointly create an effective talent training system (Liu, 2019). Proper employment of external high-quality talents plays an important role in the development of enterprises, which can bring new ideas and practices, while internal talents are more skilled and familiar with the industry, and most of them have the same values, which can form a benign talent flow mechanism and enhance team vitality (Zhou & Xie, 2018). The establishment of a good talent growth mechanism mainly involves the selection, employment, education and retention of employees. Enterprises should constantly improve the internal incentive, restraint and competition mechanisms (encourage and even require employees to learn foreign languages), create a good corporate culture, and ensure a win-win situation of enterprise and talent growth.

Moreover, it is recommended that art and craft or craft-based economy be made a part of school curriculum in educational institutions in Zengcheng, Yunfu or other cities in GBA. Students should learn art and craft from childhood, experience the charm of crafts in games, acquire inheritance consciousness of art and craft, and in the long term make due contributions to promote the legacy of local art and culture in GBA. Specifically, language-related courses should be offered in application-oriented universities in GBA to actively cultivate bilingual talents of cross-border e-commerce, so as to support enterprises to establish e-commerce platform.

Choose professional logistics services provided by third party logistics enterprises

Cross-border e-commerce, a huge market, has been carved out by several industry majors, and an increasing number of small and medium-sized cross-border e-commerce platforms have emerged.

According to Feng (2016), small and medium-sized cross-border e-commerce platforms must focus on product sales and customer maintenance. If they do not have adequate funds, time and the ability to build their own logistics system, they can only rely on third-party logistics enterprises. These third-party logistics enterprises play an important role in providing comprehensive services for small and medium-sized platforms. Besides, such small and medium-sized cross-border e-commerce platforms can outsource store decoration, advertising design, supplier quality supervision and cross-border logistics to domestic or foreign professional service providers based on the actual situation of individuals, and even employ overseas personnel to engage in online store customer service, which not only reduces costs, but prevents possible errors in the business environment.

Improve the construction of logistics infrastructure and strengthen information technology

In order to strengthen the application of information technology in cross-border e-commerce logistics, we should update emerging information technologies and equipment such as big data, cloud computing, mobile Internet, QR code, RFID, intelligent sorting system, logistics optimisation and navigation integrated system in the field of e-commerce logistics.

Improve legal mechanism and policy of cross-border e-commerce logistics

Cross-border e-commerce and cross-border e-commerce logistics can become robust and develop significantly only in a sound legal environment. Cross-border e-commerce is growing rapidly in China, and the relevant laws and regulations will become an indispensable aspect.

Build brand image with the help of film and television programmes

Through films, television programmes or documentaries, it is feasible to highlight the unique carving technology and long-standing culture of crafts. In recent years, governments at all levels in Guangdong Province have been focusing on the development of culture, but as far as cultural products are concerned, the propaganda means are still relatively simple and lack innovation. With the influence of different media such as movies and documentaries, many products with local characteristics and culture have gradually gained popularity. We can also introduce craft advertisements in films, television programmes or documentaries. It can also be accomplished by making use of the celebrity effect of traditional craftsmen. It is recommended that celebrities be invited to learn or promote art and craft through mass communication. To go a step further, governments and investors can create a few leading e-commerce-oriented companies marketing traditional crafts, and provide opportunities and a sufficient platform for them.

Conclusion

The paper suggests that bilingual cross-border e-commerce is highly accessible for the marketing of crafts in GBA. Considering bilingual service as a promotional means and cross-border e-commerce as the sales channel, this paper analysed the sales status, existing problems and development prospects of related crafts stemming from the two locations that produce crafts. Suggestions and strategies are provided through investigation and research, which offers constructive recommendation on the sale of crafts in combination with the construction, design and operation of bilingual cross-border e-commerce websites, so as to expand the domestic market, strive for overseas market of the crafts, cultivate proper talents and provide effective logistics. With a view to vigorously promoting innovation and entrepreneurship education, we should tap opportunities for the development of cross-border e-commerce to foster the business sense and capability of foreign language talents, which could not only address the problems of entrepreneurship for foreign language talents, but also promote the economic development of the region.

Limitation

Although this paper discussed accessibility of bilingual cross-border e-commerce in GBA from the case of Chinese traditional crafts, there are still limitations. On the grounds that the discussion of the bilingual cross-border e-commerce is, to a large extent, based on the field work of two cities that produce crafts, there could be other appropriate measures to the problems if other similar cities are considered. To put it another way, to validate our analysis, it is suggested to have statistical tests that require a larger sample size to ensure a representative distribution of the cases to whom results will be generalized. Thus, consistent studies on this issue should be carried on.

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